
**THE EFFECT OF GROUP COHESIVENESS AND JOB SATISFACTION
ON PRODUCTIVITY IN EMPLOYEES OF HUMAN RESOURCES
DEVELOPMENT IN THE MINISTRY OF HOME AFFAIRS**

Iman Iskandar *¹

^{*1} Management of Education Department, State University of Jakarta, Indonesia

Abstract:

The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of group investigation by sigil and The objective of the research is to obtain information about the effect of group cohesiveness and job satisfaction on productivity of the employee on Human Resource Development Agency of Ministry of Home Affairs. The research was conducted to all of employees on on Human Resource Development Agency of Ministry of Home Affairs by using a survey method with path analysis applied in testing hypothesis. The number 133 employees as sample was selected by using Slovin formula. The research conclude: (1) there is direct effect of group cohesiveness on productivity. (2) there is direct effect of job satisfaction on productivity. (3) there is direct effect of group cohesiveness on job satisfaction. Therefore, to enhance employees' productivity can be carried out by group cohesiveness, and job satisfaction.

Keywords: Group Cohesiveness; Productivity; and Job Satisfaction.

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1. Introduction

Development in the field of productive human resources is one of the keys to achieving the success of national development goals. Similarly, government institutions are fundamentally established with the aim of obtaining reliable human resources to maintain the life and development of their government institutions. To achieve this goal, government institutions can take advantage of all the capabilities and opportunities that exist as much as possible and minimize the obstacles and weaknesses they face. In achieving the goals of the organization the role of labor cannot be denied as a determinant of success.

The Secretary of the Human Resources Development Agency of the Ministry of Home Affairs stated that there were still employees who had not yet performed their roles optimally in the implementation of education and training activities, thus influencing the continuity of the schedule, service to training participants, meeting of the learning needs of each resource session, and the general effectiveness of achieving learning objectives. And he stated that there are still employees who are not responsible for their work, employee motivation towards increasing work productivity

is sometimes inconsistent. From the above problems, it can be concluded that there are still problems regarding employee productivity in the Human Resources Development Agency of the Ministry of Home Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia.

Productivity is the work of an employee. This work is a product of a person's working process towards his work. Productivity illustrates the relationship between the level of effectiveness achieved with the level of resource efficiency. As is known that every organization, both those engaged in business and non-business sectors utilize limited resources to obtain the expected result. The managed resources are workers or employees as human, machine, material, money and information resources. Human factor as the main source is the most important factor among other production factors in the organization because human resources plan, implement, and control every activity of the organization to achieve the goal. Workers or employees cannot and should not be confused with tools or factory machinery because workers are people who have diverse personalities that can affect work productivity.

The fact is often found that in conditions of work where required conditions are already fulfilled, employee work productivity is felt to be too low and why employee productivity is still low. Even always looking for reasons that employee productivity is low because of limited company resources or employee dissatisfaction. Most people interpret or perceive that unsatisfactory conditions are caused by low wages or salaries. That view admittedly is true and it cannot be denied that wages and working conditions have a large influence on work productivity, however group cohesiveness and employee job satisfaction have a greater role and influence on employee work productivity.

Productivity is defined as comparison between the results achieved (output) and the overall resources used (input). In other words, productivity has two dimensions. The first dimension is effectiveness that leads to the achievement of targets related to quality, quantity and time. The second is efficiency related to efforts in relation to inputs with the realization of their use or how the work is carried out.

The problem is determinate how to generate and increase this productivity. Some important determinants for the formation of productivity in an organization are group cohesiveness and job satisfaction. This study examines and analyzes the direct effect of group cohesiveness on productivity as well as the indirect effects mediated by job satisfaction, with the research subject being employees of the Human Resources Development Agency of the Ministry of Home Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia.

2. Materials and Methods

This research was conducted at the Human Resources Development Agency of the Ministry of Home Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia. The sample used was Simple Random Sampling with 133 employees. The method used in this study is a survey method using a questionnaire as the tool for collecting basic data and documentation.

This research uses path analysis to find out the influence between variables according to the causal model formed. Before the questionnaire was used in this study a trial was conducted to determine

the validity and reliability of the instrument. These results are used as instruments to take research data in the field. Data analysis includes: 1) description of data, 2) test prerequisites for normality analysis, 3) path analysis which includes: analysis of models, testing of hypotheses and determining the level of influence.

Picture 1: Constellation of Research Problems

Information:

X1: Group Cohesiveness

X2: Job satisfaction

X3: Productivity

3. Results and Discussions

Direct influence of group cohesiveness on productivity

Based on the results of the calculation of path analysis, the direct influence of group cohesiveness on the work productivity of employees of the Human Resource Development Agency of the Ministry of Home Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia. From the calculation results obtained the correlation coefficient $r_{13} = 0.356$ and the path coefficient value $p_{31} = 0.280$. The results of this study are in accordance with the research conducted by Jerry Gosenpud (1986: 115) which states, "one expectation about the relationship between performance and performance teams perform better than non-cohesive ones. This hypothesis has been proposed by many theorists, especially by social psychologists. For example, according to Penrod [24], a high degree of cohesiveness has several effects that should be conducive to high productivity. Thus hypothesis 1 which predicts that there is a direct effect of group cohesiveness on employee work productivity is acceptable. This reflects, the notion that the higher the group cohesiveness, the higher employee productivity.

The direct effect of job satisfaction on productivity

Based on the results of the calculation of path analysis, the direct effect of job satisfaction on the work productivity of employees of the Human Resources Development Agency of the Ministry of Home Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia. The calculation results return the correlation coefficient $r_{23} = 0.358$ and the path coefficient value $p_{32} = 0.282$. The results of this study are corroborated by opinions Research conducted by Mark G. Resheske (2008: 7) states, "It is

hypothesized that cohesion factors of group will be associated with job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is important for organizations to address due to absenteeism, (1) turnover, (2) and pro-social "citizenship" behaviors such as helping coworkers, helping customers and being more cooperative with all social ties. Literature also shows that increased productivity was found to be related to higher satisfaction. Thus hypothesis 2 which predicts that there is a direct effect of job satisfaction on employee productivity can be accepted. This reflects that the higher employee job satisfaction, the higher the employee's work productivity.

Direct influence of group cohesiveness on job satisfaction

Based on the results of the calculation of path analysis, the direct effect of group cohesiveness on the job satisfaction of the Human Resources Development Agency of the Ministry of Home Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia. From the calculation results obtained the value of the correlation coefficient $r_{12} = 0.271$ and the path coefficient value $p_{21} = 0.271$. The results of this study are in accordance with the research Research conducted by Lynne MacDonald (2012: 48) explains, "group cohesiveness occurs when members of a group enjoy strong social relationships and a shared sense of identity. Individuals are proud to describe themselves as group members and see group membership as important. Group members are committed to their tasks and take pride in the output and achievements of the group. Members of cohesive groups deal with openly and constructively conflict. Cohesive groups increase job satisfaction and reduce stress because they offer social support to team members. " Thus hypothesis 3 which predicts there is a direct effect of group cohesiveness on job satisfaction can be accepted. This reflects that the higher the group's cohesiveness, the higher employee job satisfaction.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the results of the data analysis and discussion it was concluded that there:

(1) there is a positive influence of group cohesiveness on employee work productivity, which is determined by the degree of influence in the form of correlation coefficients and path coefficients. This path coefficient value determines employee work productivity variance is determined by group cohesiveness variables. Furthermore, the significance of the effect between group cohesiveness on productivity partially. This meaning and affirmation that empirical group cohesiveness is not the only predictor variable for employee productivity productivity score variance. (2) there is a positive effect of job satisfaction on employee work productivity, which is determined by the degree of influence in the form of correlation coefficients and path coefficients. This path coefficient value determines work productivity variance is determined by the variable job satisfaction. Furthermore, the significance of the influence of job satisfaction on employee work productivity partially. This has the meaning and affirmation that empirical job satisfaction is not the only predictor variable for employee productivity productivity score variance. (3) there is a positive influence of group cohesiveness on employee job satisfaction, determined by the degree of influence in the form of correlation coefficients and path coefficients. This path coefficient value determines how much the variance of employee job satisfaction is determined by group cohesiveness variables. The significance of the influence between group cohesiveness and employee job satisfaction.

Based on the conclusions of the research, it is suggested that various efforts can be carried out in order to increase the productivity of employees of the Human Resources Development Agency of the Ministry of Home Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia as follows: comfort for subordinates. And employees must have a high work commitment to the organization and members of its working group, and employees should carry out the dimensions of group cohesiveness including: (a) social strength: Overall the impulse made by the strength or desire of individuals in the group to remain in the group, (b) Unity in groups: Feelings of belonging to the group and having moral feelings related to their membership in the group. (c) Attractiveness: Individuals will be more interested in seeing in terms of their own working group rather than seeing from their members specifically. (d) Group collaboration: Individuals have a greater desire to work together to achieve group goals. When employees are committed to carrying out all dimensions of the cohesiveness of the group it will automatically increase their work productivity. (2) to improve employee job satisfaction including improving working conditions (mainly from an employee's perspective) and greater organizational effectiveness. Collaboration between groups (group cohesiveness) can improve employee job satisfaction. If employees are very satisfied with their work and experience positive feelings while working, they can do their jobs better and choose to remain in the organization for a long time. Employees who get satisfaction in doing their jobs will survive to work longer in the company / agency where he works and will affect the increase in work productivity. and that job satisfaction is a predictor of productivity. (3) the researchers are related to the results of this study, in order to involve more predictor variables which are thought to correlate with employee work productivity.

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*Corresponding author.

E-mail address: imaniskandar30@ gmail.com